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ENVIRONMENTAL AWARENESS: THE LIABILITY OF THE ADMINISTRATION FOR THE DAMAGES CAUSED

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ABSTRACT:

This article has as its scope the responsibility of the administration for the damages caused to the environment and the lack of awareness provided by the profiles of administrators that put them at risk due to the lack of planning and organization of the place. The general objective is to analyze the environmental conscience in the face of the administration's responsibility for the damages caused. It is a methodology with a qualitative approach, succeeding in the bibliographic research. Through this there were the analyzes of books, scientific articles, and internet materials consistent with the theme that, for such production, national authors of knowledge in administration and environment were reviewed environment. Therefore, it is concluded that environmental awareness is the most effective way that can serve as a challenge to administrators and managers who have the opportunity to embrace their implementations, inserting innovative strategies during their activities process. In short, with these actions, you will be able to contribute to the collectivity that operates, thus helping to build a space that can thrive.

Keywords: Death; Mourning; Covid-19; Mental health.

INTRODUCTION

In Brazil, several business administrations internalize the concept of environmental awareness, which drives a concern with the conservation and preservation of the environment, considering that all this involves social, economic, and structural conditions. It is noticed that there is a plurality of complexities, which are listed in the responsibility for the damages caused, evidencing in the managerial dimensions, in terms of development, that converge in lousy administration.

This study was due to the environmental impacts and the lack of awareness that many business administrators do not consciously intensify the use of natural resources, socially and structurally proposing harmful ways linked to the environmental dimensions. This theme guides critical analyses, by inserting qualified scientific journals in the area of Administration, which may be productive for other academics from other areas of knowledge.

Thus, this study has as its general objective to analyze the environmental conscience in the face of the responsibility of the administration for the damages caused. So, the specific goals are: to understand the ecological conscience; understand management's responsibility for environmental damage, and analyze the importance of leadership in environmental awareness.

In this sense, the problem at hand is why is it necessary to have environmental awareness to avoid holding the administration accountable for the damage caused? This question will be answered in the course of the article, which emphasizes that raising awareness does not put the structure at risk, and an administrative action consistent with the integrity of the

environment can prevent problems causing degradation.

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ENVIRONMENTAL CONSCIOUSNESS

The environment is everything that involves the existence of life on Earth, being part of an ecology that consists of a set of chemical, social, biological, and physical elements that bring indirect or direct effects on human beings. In addition, there is a natural system composed of microorganisms, flora, fauna, atmosphere, rocks, and soils, among others, that are part of environmental phenomena. It is essential to highlight that man is the significant influencer of nature, which can establish impacting processes on the planet.

Historically, environmental processes have been impacted since the emergence of the Industrial Revolution because industries were the great precursors of atmospheric pollution and exploitation. In addition, urbanization several years has dramatically intensified the production of waste, emerging as a worrying factor in humanity's relationship with natural resources (PACHECO et al., 2019). Through all this, environmental awareness emerged, which consists of understanding the space where man is inserted.

However, "it seems then that we are in a historical moment of fundamental importance for the acquisition of a

different awareness of human relations with the natural and social environment” (DORO; SPAZZIANI, 2022, p. 21-22), which is why, the search in the analysis of environmental structures, had an intention that led to the understanding of transforming the concepts and practices for a better environment.

In general, environmental awareness came to be understood due to environmental causes, considering the short, medium, and long term impacts. It encompasses the pollution generated by various human actions and demanded resources. With this, to have a conscience in the sense of improvement, it is necessary to have a closer relationship with the environment, which may awaken some conceptions about the reflexes of nature itself. Even because all knowledge is generated in practice and can bring positive effects.

The emergence of environmental issues and climate change and the emergence of movements that are increasingly aware that we are in fact experiencing a serious problem that can jeopardize the future of the human species, brings to the fore the way in which society is actually informed about environmental issues. The emergency to solve environmental problems calls for citizens to be active and environmentally “literate”, and it makes sense to promote a “capacity” or competence in citizens, which is Environmental Literacy (MORENO; MAFRA, 2022, p. 66) .

However, raising awareness among human beings requires external factors that influence daily habits, that is, the relationships between the environment and organisms. Therefore, it can be said that preservation and human awareness of the ecological system depend on participation and understanding, involving everyone in a society through

activities that contribute to general conservation, and education through training in environmental awareness.

1.1. BRIEF CONCEPTS

The word conscientize means a conscious act linked to the human attitude, which conveys something to obtain information. In addition, awareness is a process that consists of consciously, where the individual acquires knowledge and doing, bringing a meaning that, in general, can get its own benefits, that is, an informed human being capable of dealing with the most diverse situations. Criticism, obtaining experiences or insights that suit you on a particular subject.

About environmental awareness, it is the creation or transformation of a critical sense about the damage caused to the environment, due to exploitation caused damage, resulting in the precision of human care. It can be said that it is an introspective process that requires the individual to acquire thoughts that aim at the rationality of conservation (HARTMANN, 2010). When talking about this subject, he inserts that in Brazil, there are several educational means to promote the conscientious issue of nature, for example, legislation, and warnings, among others.

[...] the fragmentation and sectoralization of administrative action, insufficiently compensated by coordination and integration mechanisms, and the inadequacy of territorial organization, involving types of territorial cuts, division of responsibilities between them and definition of the relationships between the different levels, in mechanisms view of the project of an integrated management of resources and natural environments.

Environmental awareness is a form of

conscious education, which represents fundamental instruments in the form of thinking for possible transformations of the damage caused to the environment. In addition, environmental degradation is a complex factor that requires educational practices with a transforming function, such as, for example, individuals who are aware of actions that make it essential for a better and sustainable world (KLOETZEL, 2017).

By Ramos et al. (2021, p. 85), environmental problems arise from,

[...] the fragmentation and sectoralization of administrative action, insufficiently compensated by coordination and integration mechanisms, and the inadequacy of territorial organization, involving types of territorial cuts, division of responsibilities between them and definition of the relationships between the different levels, in view of the project of an integrated management of resources and natural environments.

Therefore, the primary function of environmental awareness is to show the relevance of the various ramifications that make human beings aware of maintaining a balance since, for sustainable practices, accountability is needed, which becomes broad, as it consists of various sectors that influence the structuring of the environment, also considering the involvement of managers both environmentally and administratively, this because, being linked to the conservation of places and natural resources.

ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACTS AND MANAGEMENT MANAGEMENT

The environment is structured in impacts due to procedures that meet expectations and needs for an associated societal improvement. Previously, the problems are implanted due to the

operationalization of the enterprises established by the managers, which come through instruments and plans that impact the spaces, as well as mitigate complexity that degrades the natural resources; such identifications consist of the activities, services, and productions that negatively generate degradations. However, "in all segments of this legal discipline, the aspect of preventing environmental damage stands out" (BENJAMIN, 2006, p. 14).

However, organizational performance generates several positive and negative aspects, which play an essential role in managing development models that require rational management, mainly when referring to responsibilities around natural resources (BORTOLASO, 2021). The administrator is responsible mainly for minimizing environmental impacts and promoting a balance that is in accordance with the productive needs that characterize the maintenance of the place.

As Benjamin (2006, p. 01) explains:

[...] environmental protection is directly related to the issue of administrative discretion. Environmental protection, over time, has always been at the expense of the environment. More and more restraints are imposed on the administrator, always with the aim of strengthening his preservationist vein, weakening his eco-mutilator side.

In this context, the administrator must have a strategic dimension to plan development without impacting the environment. Furthermore, it is necessary to maintain and implement environmental policies that promote sustainability, characterized by actions and procedures consistent with the protection and preservation of the place.

The integrity of physical environments and social groups depends on the monitoring and controlling the fundamental instruments that bring the quality of services (AROEIRA, 2022).

Therefore, the administration of managers is of mere importance because it consists of activities and services which are performed in an interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary way to achieve positive results about the structure of the place (BARBIERI; SILVA, 2020). However, a good administrator always has a holistic view to reducing environmental impacts caused by human action and needs administrative rationality that minimizes the damage caused.

THE RESPONSIBILITY OF THE ADMINISTRATION GIVEN TO ENVIRONMENTAL DAMAGE

As seen, environmental awareness brings significant factors when it is conducted with good management. The administrative responsibility about the environment is based on the damage caused, having as content in art. 70 of Law No. 9,605/98, providing for the administrative infraction, in which every action and omission is considered an environmental crime. As a general rule, other legal instruments mention the offending agent for imposing a fine, consisting of criminal and civil liability (SILVA, 2007).

It should be noted that Garcia et al. (2020) clarified that, "because of the exploratory activity, there is a concern about the damage that can occur to the environment and how the repair could occur if it occurred"; thus, there can be means for accountability over fall in the face of the administrator.

Administrative responsibility results from infractions of the administrative

rules that, consequently, the administrator is subject to punishment, warning, fine, or interdiction of the activity. Therefore, the damage caused to the environment becomes significant, which, during the year, becomes responsible for goods that affect the community, taking into account that all this happened due to the lack of planning and organization, which they are fundamental for avoiding future consequences.

Provisions for environmental crimes are added, inserting any ecological damage resulting from mismanagement; that is, for infractions to the environment, administrative sanctions are consigned to those individuals, this is because, the prescriptions that compete in accountability will consist according to the disciplinary norm (BLIACHERIS; FERREIRA, 2012). It is worth mentioning that every manager or administrator is responsible for preserving and managing their heritage, attributing to environmental conservation through good planning and organization.

In this way, it can be said that responsibility in the administrative sphere and punishment for damages caused to the environment consists even, then, of more significant harm, for requiring repair, sometimes tricky, for taking time to achieve a restoration (CHIAVENATO, 2000). Therefore, having administrative awareness about environmental appeals, processing development and organization will bring greater credibility and visibility, as it does not harm natural resources.

THE IMPORTANCE OF ADMINISTRATION IN ENVIRONMENTAL AWARENESS

Analyzing the whole context, it is understood that administrative

environmental awareness is nothing more than an entirely preserved and organized environment. In addition, the search for information is a factor that keeps any administrator or manager up to date since the combination of its attribution in a conscientious way brings alert to the risks and impacts that damage not only structural but to the collectivity. It is noticed that there is vitality throughout the administrative process, which can present measures and solutions that can be taken to reduce the causing effects.

The role of environmental awareness in the administrative relationship is to create sustainable thinking in order to reduce the impacts caused to the environment. That is, when a process is carried out within a company, mentalities with shared decisions can occur in the way of thinking with other individuals, whether friends, or employees, among others. In addition, it is essential to consider a preserved space or place because putting simple measures into practice can make a difference, mainly avoiding responsibility for the illegality of damages caused to the environment (SOUZA FILHO, 2020).

The Ministry of the Environment has structured six thematic axes for the importance of implementation in administrative services, which they have: The “rational use of natural resources and public goods; management of generated waste; quality of life in the work environment; awareness and training of servers; sustainable public procurement; sustainable constructions,” which are used as programs to maintain the sustainability and conservation of the site (MMA, 2022).

Taking good care of a company or space is to think that the way other people treat the environment is to

becoming aware of the need for change to avoid environmental impacts. Some economic and social transformations are fundamental for ecological preservation, not least because many people already have a sharp vision for conscious consumption. For example, sustainable buildings, and concern for energy savings, among other aspects. It should be noted that, in administration, environmental awareness happens progressively. However, attitudes can reduce environmental damage.

Environmental awareness in the management relationship aims to transform the agents’ habits in implementing responsibility in their administrative functions. By the way, attitudes and practices that reduce the wear and tear of activities can prevent the unruly form that causes the environment. Sustainable actions in services, seek adoption for new patterns of consumption and reduction, among others. This is an awareness that managers or administrators can harbor for the importance of such issues.

Today, there is a need for organizations to work with policies aimed at environmental issues, showing that the market gains provided by this new administrative approach can mean the permanence of these companies in their market, in addition to enabling the gain of new markets (FRACASSO, 2011, p. 24).

Therefore, encourage criteria and principles that involve environmental implementation in routine activities, encouraging and promoting the adoption and implementation of actions consisting of responsibility for the environment, envisioning the collectivity and personal engagement for everyone involved in the services.

CONCLUSION

Analyzing everything exposed in this article, it was observed that environmental awareness is directly linked to sustainability, giving meaning to its actions and practices that preserve resources. It is understood that making human beings aware can influence different habits in everyday life, passing a segment that raises participation and sensitivity that contribute to the conservation of space. It is noted that lifestyle changes bring attitudes that differentiate the routine socially, collectively, and individually.

In this way, it is clear that the primary function of environmental awareness is to branch out and maintain a balance between people, using in a concertizing way everything that involves their needs. Therefore, observing sustainable practices, it was understood that there is a precision for accountability, broadening the most varied influence regarding the structuring of the environment. So, it became clear that managers are primarily responsible for keeping their administrative form linked to the conservation of the site.

However, environmental impacts are factors with numerous problems, and can thus cause a process that holds managers responsible during their administrative functions, for harming the environment. With this, it is suggested that a strong orientation towards the segments of customs, habits, among other aspects that are highly protected and valued during the permanence of collective and individual activities. Therefore, innovations and cooperation between individuals present themselves, therefore, as the most promising alternatives for site conservation.

That said, it is noted that administrative

responsibility in relation to damage caused to the environment is conditioned by the use of activities, goods, among others for the benefit of the community, which can be punished with sanctions or fines, in cases of infractions. It follows that, in the event of such action, within the limits of their respective ones, they may be enshrined in the legislation that pertains to the case, individually, since it is observed that the behaviors affect or can affect the entire structure of the environment.

Therefore, it is concluded that environmental awareness is the most effective way that can serve as a challenge to administrators and managers who have the opportunity to embrace with their implementations, inserting innovative strategies during their activities process. In short, with these actions you will be able to contribute to the collectivity that operates, thus helping to build a space that can thrive.

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